

Editorial

Haptoglobin Phenotype, Serum Iron Levels and Severity in Multi-Drug Resistant Mycobacterium Tuberculosis Patients in Ibadan

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Haptoglobin Phenotype, Serum Iron Levels and Severity in Multi-Drug Resistant Mycobacterium Tuberculosis Patients in Ibadan

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Abstract: Haptoglobin (Hp) phenotypes possess biochemical and functional efficiencies accounting for distinct antioxidant and immuno-modulatory capacities. Hp 2.2 phenotype has been observed as a genetic risk factor for several infectious diseases, including Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB). Nigeria is ranked 4th globally, with 590,000 cases, the increase in antibiotic resistance worldwide, has called for better personalized treatment on a genetic level, as patients with multi-drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) need to undergo extended, expensive, and hazardous second-line therapy. Given that iron homeostasis is crucial for the microbiological growth of MTB, the objective of this work was to observe the relationship and investigate possible associations with the Hp phenotypes as well as CRP concentrations measuring severity in TB patients. Fifty (50) clinically and Laboratory diagnosed tuberculosis patients were classified by the Gene-Xpert system into MDR-TB (25) and DS-TB (25) and 25 health control were recruited for the study after ethical clearance. Haptoglobin phenotypes were determined using electrophoresis while plasma iron and CRP levels were determined through spectrophotometry using kits obtainable from My BioSource Inc. The Haptoglobin phenotype distribution (Hp 1.1, Hp 2.1, and Hp 2.2) showed the following: MDR-TB population, 5(20%), 7 (28%), and 13 (52%). Overall, MDR-TB represents a severe spectrum of the disease compared to control due to increased levels of inflammation and increased serum iron, influenced by haptoglobin 2-2 phenotype. Hp 2-2 positively correlated with increased Fe and CRP levels (0.014) and (p=0.009) respectively but not with Hp 1-1 and Hp 2-2 phenotypes. The Hp 2.2 phenotype prevalence in the MDR-TB population can be used as a predictive/predisposing factor to determine the trend for individuals who contract TB. The Hp 2-2 gene polymorph is almost exclusive to the African race explaining the high cases of TB. It is therefore important to know all risk factors, especially on a genetic level, to better understand and manage the disease.

Key Words: Haptoglobin, Genetics, Tuberculosis, Iron, Gene-Xpert, SSS

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, it is estimated that TB infects one in every four people in the world (World Health Organization, 2022). Each year, 1% of the population develops new infections. Over 10 million cases of active TB were reported in 2017, leading to 1.6 million deaths worldwide (World Health Organization, 2013). Of these deaths, 95% happened in developing nations (World Health Organization, 2008). Humans have been

infected with tuberculosis since antiquity, and the origin of transmission is unknown (Gan *et al.*, 2004; World Health Organization, 2013). Tubercular degradation was discovered in the spines of Egyptian mummies and cattle. Nigeria is ranked second in Africa and seventh worldwide as having the highest TB burden. In Nigeria, the incidence rate of TB is estimated to be 322 cases per 100,000 people, with only 15% of the overall burden being reported (Khazaei *et al.*, 2013).

Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) bacteria are the source of the infectious illness tuberculosis (TB). The majority of infections do not manifest any symptoms; this is known as latent tuberculosis. Tuberculosis often affects the lungs, but it can also affect other body regions or organs (Barnes, 2000). 10% of these dormant infections will become active diseases if untreated, killing 50% of those who are infected. Traditional signs of active tuberculosis include persistent coughing that produces sputum that contains blood, night sweats, fevers, and weight loss. Historically, it was referred to as "consumption" because of weight loss (Arredouani *et al.*, 2005). Extra-pulmonary tuberculosis patients can present with a variety of symptoms (Khazaei *et al.*, 2013). When individuals with active TB in their lungs cough, spit, speak, or sneeze, it spreads via the air (World Health Organization, 2022). Latent TB carriers do not spread the illness (World Health Organization, 2013). People with HIV/AIDS and smokers are more likely to have an active infection. Chest X-rays, microscopic inspection, and body fluid culture are used to diagnose active TB. 6. Blood tests or the tuberculin skin test (TST) are used to diagnose latent TB (Khazaei *et al.*, 2013).

Screening those at high risk for early detection, treatment, and immunization with the bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine is all part of the prevention of tuberculosis (TB). People at the home, place of employment, and social contacts of those with active TB are at a high risk. Treatment involves using numerous antibiotics over an extended period. As antibiotic resistance increases globally, more cases of extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) and multiple drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) are being recorded. Gene-Xpert System is used to identify the MDR gene in TB disease early diagnosis. HIV, overcrowding, subpar housing systems, hunger and smoking are risk factors for TB (World Health Organization, 2013).

Haptoglobin is produced in the liver, a plasma alpha-2 sialoglycoprotein, which is composed of two distinct polypeptide chains. All individuals have the same chains, which are polymorphic and have two dominant alleles, Hp 1

and Hp 2, which have partial dominance. Haptoglobin has three main phenotypes: Hp 1-1, Hp 2-1, and Hp 2-2 (Arredouani *et al.*, 2005). By binding, this protein stops iron from leaving the body through the kidneys, keeping it for erythropoiesis and other uses. Haptoglobin in humans is polymorphic, with the three main phenotypes being Hp 1-1, Hp 2-1, and Hp 2-2, which may be identified by gel electrophoresis. On chromosome 16, there is a gene for haptoglobin (16q22.2 which is between 72,054,505 bp to 72,061,055 bp). Polymorphic distribution can vary between ethnic and geographical locations, however, Hp 2-1 is the most prevalent phenotype (Arredouani *et al.*, 2005). Individuals with Hp 1-1 have the highest haptoglobin concentration, followed by those with Hp 2-1 and Hp 2-2, respectively. Increased vulnerability to various illnesses, such as TB, has been associated with those who have the Hp 2-2 phenotype TB (Khazaei *et al.*, 2013).

People who are iron deficient are typically more susceptible to TB (World Health Organization, 2013). The protein shields the lungs from inflammatory substances and prevents lung damage. Emphysema and COPD begin when a deficiency causes the natural bacteriostatic neutrophil activity in the body to destroy lung tissue (Fedoseeva *et al.*, 1993). Controlling microorganisms, sporadic epidemics caused by drug-resistant microorganisms and unidentified pathogenic microbial species pose a critical threat to public health (Eckersall, 2000). Infectious diseases significantly contribute to morbidity and mortality worldwide, accounting for roughly 50% of all deaths in tropical countries.

According to Kasvosve *et al.* (2000), people with the Hp 2-2 phenotype had 6.1 times greater mortality rates from tuberculosis than those with the Hp 1-1 phenotype. Additionally, in individuals with extensive cavities due to tissue loss, Hp 2-2 phenotype was overrepresented in patients with more advanced dissemination and nephrotic TB (Eckersall, 2000; Ubaïdullaev *et al.*, 2002). These unfavourable health trends necessitate an international effort to create fresh approaches to the prevention and treatment of infectious diseases. Realizing the urgent need to evaluate every possible risk factor, particularly on a genetic level, to better understand and manage the disease given the epidemic of antibiotic resistance and to promote a better future for humanity on Earth. Given that the Hp 2:2 phenotype was found to increase the risk of dying from TB (a result observed in multiple research works). Therefore, it is crucial to look at how the Hp phenotype and drug-sensitive TB and multidrug-resistant TB are related in Nigerian populations.

A. Objectives of the Study

To achieve the aim of this study, the following tasks were placed:

- To observe the distribution of haptoglobin phenotype.
- To investigate any possible associations between Hp phenotypes, serum iron and CRP concentrations that measured severity in Tb patients.
- To observe Hp phenotypes as possible genetic predisposing factors.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Haptoglobin locus is located on the long arm of chromosome 16 (16q22). Because the loci for the chains are linked to one another, a single mRNA creates a long polypeptide chain that

is cleaved to produce the two Hp chains (Soejima *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 1: Polymeric Hp 1-1, 2-1, and 2-2 structures.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Polymeric-structures-of-Hp-1-1-2-1-and-2-2-Haptoglobin-polymers-are-made-up-of-ab_fig1_300390198

Haptoglobin polymers are composed of $(\alpha\beta)$ units with various numbers of -thiol groups in position $\alpha_1\beta$ and position $\alpha_2\beta$. From Figure 1:

A) A diagram showing the α_1 and β chains, respectively, that are encoded by the Hp 1 and Hp 2 alleles. A basic unit that forms a chain is always linked to by Cys-72's -COOH terminal in position 1 α . While 2 has a tandem repeat of residues 12-70, 2 is "trivalent" because Cys-15 and -74 link to other units.

B) A diagrammatic representation of how the repeat unit (n) is arranged in each Hp phenotype.

C) 7% Native-PAGE of Hp-hemoglobin complexes displaying each phenotype's distinctive polymeric pattern. For HP phenotyping, these complexes are employed. It should be noted that there is a relatively little quantity of cyclic Hp 2-2 trimer, or $(\alpha_2\beta)_3$.

A. Association between Haptoglobin Phenotypes and Diseases

Relationships between Hp phenotypes and heart disease have been a subject of interest for many years (Ubaïdullaev *et al.*, 2002). The Hp 2-2 phenotype correlating to high-risk cardiac patients reported a significant increase in the incidence

compared to healthy control groups. Myocardial infarction followed by extensive damage was understood to be more problematic with Hp 2-2 than in other phenotypes (Van Vlierberghe *et al.*, 2004). The Hp 2-2 phenotype is an additional genetic risk factor for coronary atherosclerosis, independent of established risk factors like smoking, high cholesterol, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus. In atherosclerotic plaques, this phenotype is also known to offer less protection against oxidative stress, which may result in the development of refractory hypertension. Better blood pressure management requires patients with this phenotype to undergo complex anti-hypertensive drug combinations. Hp may be used to forecast a patient's prognosis and cardiovascular disease due to its diverse biological roles and functions (S. E. Yang *et al.*, 2000). This polymorphism may be involved in several infectious diseases, according to studies. Haptoglobin can function as a natural bacteriostat by restricting the consumption of iron necessary for the growth of various dangerous bacteria, including *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, and *Bacteroides fragilis* (Van Vlierberghe *et al.*, 2004).

Hp was discovered to be a substitute CD11b/CD18 ligand in HIV, indicating that this protein is crucial to the infection (Ubaïdullaev *et al.*, 2002). Additionally, Hp 2-2 patients had a greater mortality and even worse prognosis due to Hb-driven oxidative stress, which could be exacerbated by residual iron circulating in HIV-seropositive patients' plasma and encouraging viral proliferation and transmission. According to a documented relationship between hepatitis C and Hp polymorphism (Hp 1-1 was overrepresented), the Hp phenotype may have an impact on how hepatitis C develops clinically. It's interesting to note that people with the Hp 2-2 phenotype produce less hepatitis B antibody response after vaccination than people with other phenotypes.

In a different study, Sudanese patients with both simple and severe (cerebral) falciparum malaria had a significantly higher incidence of Hp 1-1 individuals. Among patients, the phenotypic frequency distribution for Hp 1-1, Hp 2-1, and Hp 2-2 was 60.8%, 29.7% and 9.5% respectively, while in healthy (control) persons, it was 26.0%, 55.8% and 18.3% (Ubaïdullaev *et al.*, 2002). A different study, one which involves malaria, revealed a comparable link. Hp 1-1 infection and severe *P. falciparum* malaria in patients from Ghana's coastal region.

B. Role of Iron in Immune Response

Almost all known species depend heavily on iron for growth and survival. Depriving pathogens of this crucial nutrient is a key tactic in the antimicrobial defence of mammalian species (Quaye *et al.*, 2000). The transporter responsible for pumping iron out of the phagosome, NRAMP1, is one of the most well-studied examples of this technique. Numerous studies using mouse models and tissue culture have demonstrated that the ability of NRAMP1 to reduce phagosomal iron content is essential for the survival and proliferation of several intracellular infections. These pathogens include *Leishmania donovani*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, and *Mycobacterium bovis* BCG. Polymorphisms in the NRAMP1 gene have been associated with leprosy and tuberculosis susceptibility (Delanghe *et al.*, 1999).

It was shown that upregulating FPN expression in response

to hepcidin had the opposite effect of significantly inhibiting intracellular *Salmonella* growth in either HeLa cells or J774 murine macrophages (Willemetz *et al.*, 2017). A gene in bacteria that is expressed more when there is low iron concentration was shown to be connected with elevated FPN levels, leading researchers to conclude that FPN-mediated iron efflux ultimately caused the element to be depleted in the pathogen's immediate microenvironment. With the use of iron-regulated transcriptional reporters, *Salmonella* strains were altered. Based on these first-hand accounts, multiple other teams have replicated related findings using *Salmonella* and other intracellular bacterial infections including *Legionella pneumophila*, *Chlamydia psittaci*, *C. trachomatis*, and *M. tuberculosis* (Van Vlierberghe *et al.*, 2004). According to research demonstrating that activation of macrophages, whether by bacterial infection or by interferon, is connected with transcriptional up-regulation of FPN, it may be a fundamental component of the phagocyte antimicrobial reserve. It is important to note that a variety of increased FPN gene transcription effects 3; 2 may reduce lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced hepcidin synthesis in macrophages.

C. Iron and Virulence of *M. Tuberculosis*

Siderocalin can bind to a separate class of siderophores known as the carboxymycobactins that are produced by *M. tuberculosis* and other mycobacteria in addition to its capacity to isolate enterobactin-like siderophores. In opposition to this finding, Kasvosve *et al.* (2000) showed that siderocalin is involved in preventing the growth of *M. tuberculosis* both in vitro and in vivo. Similar investigations found that the addition of recombinant siderocalin significantly reduced *M. tuberculosis* growth in both bacterial media and mice macrophages (Johnson *et al.*, 2010). Research on the contacts of people with active pulmonary tuberculosis patients revealed that siderocalin also has a function in human defence against the disease (Cherayil, 2011). The majority of cases of this infection were observed in people of African heritage; this finding was associated with decreased serum siderocalin concentrations and circulating neutrophil counts. Combinatorially, serum siderocalin levels were shown to be low in HIV-infected people, which may contribute to both pathways of immunity being disrupted and lower resistance to *M. tuberculosis* (Ferri, 2011).

D. Serum Iron in Relation to Drug Sensitivity and Multiple-Drug Sensitivity

It is urgently necessary to conduct research into new targets and processes because *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) acquired multidrug resistance (MDR) by repeated use of antitubercular medications. MTB's capacity to detect and adapt to a variety of alterations in the host is crucial for survival and is the basis of infection (World Health Organization, 2013). Iron deficiency is a critical issue that *M. tuberculosis* must overcome at the beginning of the infection since both bacteria and human systems need iron. A study examined the effects of iron deficiency on the susceptibilities of *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, a "surrogate of MTB," to recognise anti-TB medications. Results revealed that iron deficiency increased the potency of the majority of first-line anti-TB medicines, which may be reduced by taking an iron supplement. Additionally, iron appears to be necessary to maintain genotoxicity, indicating the potential involvement of iron in the DNA repair system. When these parameters

were considered, for the first time a connection between cellular iron and mycobacteria's drug sensitivity was discovered, proposing iron as a new determinant to fight MDR in tuberculosis infection (Ferri, 2011).

E. Haptoglobin Polymorphism and Iron Homeostasis
Haptoglobin collects haemoglobin that has escaped into the plasma and transports it to the parenchymal cells of the liver and ultimately to macrophages. There is no evidence to support the idea that the haptoglobin pathway is a significant barrier to iron homeostasis (Jacob *et al.*, 2009). However, it was revealed that those who were homozygous for the Hp 2 gene had higher levels of serum iron, transferrin saturation, and ferritin in their bodies for unknown reasons (in read literature) (Beutler *et al.*, 2002).

F. C-Reactive Protein in Relation to Drug Sensitivity and Multiple-Drug Sensitivity.

CRP levels increase quickly during infectious or inflammatory illness states within the first 6 to 8 hours and after 48 hours (Bento *et al.*, 2011). The levels of fibrinogen and CRP may therefore help predict the progression of TB and the success of the anti-tubercular treatment since pulmonary-reactive protein (CRP) is an acute-phase protein that serves as an early marker of tuberculosis, an inflammatory disease. In earlier research, patients with TB had significantly elevated CRP levels between 10 and 100 mg/L (Chandrashekhara, 2014). The study measured CRP levels in patients with TB of various severity levels (drug-sensitive and drug-resistant) as well as in multi-drug-resistant TB patients undergoing therapy. To distinguish between the two types of TB patients and track therapy response in MDR-TB, it is necessary to determine the utility of these acute phase proteins (Bento *et al.*, 2011; Chandrashekhara, 2014).

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Ethical Clearance

Ethical Clearance from Oyo State Human Research Ethical Committee Ministry of Health, Oyo State.

1. Recruitment of Patients

Seventy-five (75) human samples were collected, and 10 ml of blood was collected once. 50 diagnosed TB patients, from Oyo State Chest Clinic, Jericho, Ibadan. 25 Tb free individuals as control from the blood bank of UCH. Exemption of Patients on iron supplements. (The sampling carried out in the course of this work was not random but purposive sampling).

B. Materials

- Plain bottles were used in the collection of whole blood samples.
- Needles and 10 ml syringes.

1. Equipment

Gel electrophoresis; power pack and tank

2. Reagents

Haptoglobin Phenotype (Hp) Standard: 2.1, 2.2 and 1.1 obtainable from MyBioSource INC

C. Methods of Research

Laboratory analyses were done using the following methods:

- a. Human C-Reactive Protein

- b. Serum Iron

- c. Haptoglobin Phenotype (Hp) Standard: 2.1, 2.2 and 1.1

D. Methodology

Preparation of Blood Samples: Blood was collected via venipuncture. The serum was then separated from the cells after clotting by centrifugation. For plasma samples, blood was collected into a container in a plain bottle and then centrifuged. Care was taken to minimize hemolysis.

E. Methods

1. Human C-Reactive Protein Test.

Reagent Preparation

Before usage, reagents should be at room temperature (18–25 °C). The patient's serum was 100 times diluted before usage. Several tiny tubes (i.e., 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes) were made, and 5 ml of serum was mixed with 495 ml (0.495 ml).

Sample Preparation

- a. For this test, serum samples were used.
- b. Standard venipuncture procedures were used to obtain the specimens. Within 60 minutes of the serum being collected, it was extracted from the packed or coagulate cells.
- c. Specimens were frozen at -20°C or below if they weren't analyzed within 24 hours of collection.
- d. Avoid samples that are grossly lipemic (milky), grossly hemolytic (bright red), or cloudy (after centrifugation).

C-reactive protein (CRP) is measured using this technique's latex-enhanced nephelometry. A soluble analyte and the matching antigen or antibody attached to polystyrene particles react in particle-enhanced tests. Anti-CRP antibodies are covalently linked to particles with a polystyrene core and a hydrophilic shell to quantify CRP. Latex particles coated with mouse monoclonal anti-CRP antibodies are combined with a diluted solution of the test sample. The test sample's CRP will combine with the latex particles to form an antigen-antibody combination. After six minutes, the amount of light scattering, as determined by a nephelometric method, is inversely proportional to the amount of analyte in the sample. There is an automated blank subtraction. A calibration curve is used to calculate CRP concentrations.

2. Serum Iron Procedure

Reagent Preparation

- a. Combining 3 g/dL sodium chloride and 0.2 mol/L hydrochloric acid: A 2-L flask containing 250 mL of deionized water was filled with 34 mL of concentrated HCl and 60 g of NaCl. Mixed thoroughly and diluted with deionized water to volume. (This solution was made as needed to be utilized as a component of the working solution; it remained stable at 20 to 25°C.)
- b. A working solution of HCl, NaCl, and Brj: 20 drops of Brij were added to 200 mL of 0.2 mol/L HCl and 3 g/dL NaCl and thoroughly mixed for every 150 samples that needed to be tested.
- c. Using HCl, NaCl, and ascorbic acid as a solution: Add 1 g of L-ascorbic acid and 10 drops of Brij to 100 mL of 0.2 mol/L HCl with 3 g/dL NaCl for every 150 samples that need to be tested. Mix thoroughly.
- d. Buffer with 0.75 mol/L acetate: Then, in a 4-L flask containing 2 L of deionized water, 408.1 g of sodium

- acetate was added. This needs to be made once a week; the solution is stable between 20 and 25 degrees Celsius.
- Ferrozine 0.07 g/dL with 1% (w/v) thiourea: To 1 L of the acetate buffer-thiourea solution, 0.7 g of ferrozine and 10 g of thiourea were added and thoroughly mixed. Removed after filtering through a 0.45-µm Millipore. Additionally, any undissolved particles. (Weekly preparation; solution stable at 20–25 °C.)
 - Brij-35 wash solution, 0.5 ml/L (v/v): 2 L of deionized water was combined with 1 mL of Brij-35, 30% solution.
 - Hydrochloric acid, 0.1 mol/L (for standard preparation): In a 1-L volumetric flask, 8.3 mL of concentrated HCl was added to 500 mL of deionized water. Combined thoroughly and diluted to volume with more water. Brij-35 was left out. To prepare intermediate and working standards, approximately 5 L of this solution are needed.
 - Iron-saturating solution for TIBC at 400 L/dL: A 500 mL flask containing deionized water was filled with 2.0 mL of the 1.0 g/L stock iron standard. (Moved to a plastic storage bottle and given a week to settle before use. At 20 to 25 °C, the solution is stable.)

Standards Development (allow standards to equilibrate for 24–72 hours)

- g/L standard solution for stock iron: One volumetric litre was filled with one kilogram of iron wire. With a little heat, 12 mL of strong HCl was added, dissolving the wire. The flask was allowed to cool to ambient temperature when the wire had completely disintegrated, and the contents were then diluted to volume with deionized water. (The solution is stable when kept at 20 to 25 °C in a polypropylene container.)
- iron intermediate stock solution at 50.0 mg/L: With 0.1 mol/L of HCl, 25 mL of the 1.0 g/L stock iron solution is diluted to make 500 mL.
- Iron standards in use: Prepare dilutions from the intermediate standard as shown below in a series of 500 mL volumetric flasks. Mix well after dilution to 500 mL with 0.1 mol/L HCl. (As needed; the solution is stable between 20 and 25 °C.) Standard reference material can be diluted at concentrations between 1 and 1000 L/dL to check the correctness of the working standard dilutions. It has a concentration of 1.0001 mg/mL.

Reportable Normal Ranges

Males >18 years old: 60-190 µL/dL iron; Females >18 years old: 40-175 µL/dL iron and Children 3-17 years old: 32-175 µL/dL iron.

3. Haptoglobin Typing

- Standards: In 1mL of double-distilled water (final concentration 1g/L), purified haptoglobin phenotypic standards (My Biosource, Inc.) were dissolved, aliquoted, and kept at -30°C.
- Free haemoglobin: After being cleansed twice with 0.9% (v/v) saline, whole blood was diluted with double-distilled water to a concentration of around 10% haemoglobin, which was then measured by a Coulter counter using the cyanomethaemoglobin method. At 4°C, this solution was kept.
- Electrophoresis: Electrophoresis was completed in its entirety. The kits came with the citratemaleate electrophoresis buffer (pH 6.2).
- Stain: Just before use, the stain was prepared. It comprised 1mL of 1% (w/v) potassium ferricyanide,

150J.L of 30% (w/v) hydrogen peroxide, 5mL of 0.22% (w/v) 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine in methanol, 5mL of dimethylsulphoxide, and 1mL each of glacial acetic acid and 1% (w/v) potassium ferricyanide.

- Fixative/destain: Glacial acetic acid was combined with methanol and double-distilled water in a 2:1:1 ratio.

Electrophoresis

Free haemoglobin (5 J.L) was added to 95 J.L of serum samples from patients or haptoglobin standards. The samples were vortexed for five minutes and then permitted to stand for the formation of the haptoglobin-haemoglobin complex. Aliquots (3 J.L) of each sample were loaded onto the gel using a template, and electrophoretic separation was carried out for 35 min at 50 V and 20 mA (or by the manufacturer's instructions). Gels were destained for two 5-minute washes in gel fixative after staining for 10 minutes at the end of each run. Gels were rinsed with tap water and dried in the sun to avoid fading, in an oven at 65°C for 30 min., and then stored at room temperature without exposure to light.

Figure 2: Electrophoresis

Note: samples were already differentiated and characterised by the Gene-Xpert machine upon collection. and then subjected to the test procedures listed above.

Figure 3: Layout of GeneXpert Assay

F. Data Analysis

Hardy Weinberg Equilibrium was used to check for genotypic predisposition, allelic frequency and phenotypic distribution. Data obtained were analysed using SPSS. Analysis for Homogeneity of the groups. Student's t-test and Chi-square were used to check the differences between the two groups. ANOVA was used to find significance between the mean and standard deviation of study groups. Kruskal Wallis was used to test the differences between study groups. Pearson's correlation was used to find the correlation

between groups. Statistical significance (p) will be at < 0.05 and 95% confidence interval.

IV. RESULTS

The results of the between haptoglobin phenotype, serum iron, the severity of MDR and DS Tubercle bacilli are displayed below:

Table 1: Haptoglobin Phenotype Distribution and Allele Frequency in MDR-TB Population

Groups	Haptoglobin Phenotypes Distribution			Hp Allele Frequency	
	Hp 1-1	Hp 2-1	Hp 2-2	Hp 1	Hp 2
MDR-TB	5 (20%)	7 (28%)	13 (52%)	0.34	0.66
Control	10 (40%)	10 (40%)	5 (20%)	0.6	0.4

P-value is significant at ≤ 0.05

Table 2: Plasma iron and CRP Concentrations in MDR-TB and Control Population

Parameters	MDR-TB	Control	P-value
Fe	85.60±27.82	84.68±36.77	0.921
CRP	24.37±23.63	2.6±1.72	0.001*

P-value is significant at ≤ 0.05

Table 3: Correlation between Haptoglobin Phenotypes, Serum Iron and CRP in MDR-TB Population

Parameters	Fe r(p)	CRP r(p)
Hp 1-1	-0.017 (0.935)	0.000 (0.998)
Hp 2-1	0.025 (0.905)	-0.134 (0.525)
Hp 2-2	1.01 (0.014)*	1.297 (0.009)*

P-value is significant at ≤ 0.05

V. DISCUSSION

In this study, the MDR-TB population, 5 (20%) had the Hp 1-1 phenotype, 7 (28 %) had the Hp 2-1 phenotype, and 13 (52%) had the Hp 2-2 phenotype. While in the control group, 10 (40%) samples had the Hp 1-1 phenotype, 10 (40%) had the Hp 2-1 phenotype, and 5 (20%) had the Hp 2-2 phenotype. Using Hardy Weinberg equilibrium principle allelic frequency, MDR-TB had a distribution of 0.34 for Hp 1 and 0.66 for Hp 2 while Control had a distribution of 0.6 for Hp 1 and 0.4 for Hp 2 showing that it could be a genetic predictive biomarker but not predisposing factor to this infection. It was also observed that there were more individuals with the Hp 2-2 phenotype than any of the three phenotypes with Hp 1-1 having the lowest frequency. However, this result could be better validated with a larger sample size associated with genetic studies.

Studies have linked the Hp 2-2 phenotype to higher rates of morbidity from illnesses like diabetes, HIV infection, and cardiovascular disease. The highest levels of haptoglobin are found in those with Hp 1-1 > Hp 2.1 > Hp 2-2 (Arredouani *et al.*, 2005). Hp 2-2 has also been linked to higher serum ferritin levels, increased susceptibility to infections including

TB, and increased macrophage iron buildup (Fedoseeva *et al.*, 1993).

Lack of haptoglobin in tuberculosis can cause lung tissue to be destroyed by bacteriostatic neutrophil action, which can result in the start of emphysema and COPD (F. Yang *et al.*, 2000). Additionally, patients with extensive cavities caused by tissue damage, more advanced dissemination, and the presence of nephritic TB were overrepresented in the Hp 2-2 phenotype (Fedoseeva *et al.*, 1993; Ubaïdullaev *et al.*, 2002). The lungs are more vulnerable to metal-induced oxidative stress than any other organ in the body because of their special anatomical function in high-volume oxygen exchange and big blood supply.

Due to an elevated amount of inflammation, MDR-TB generally indicates a severe spectrum of the disease in comparison to control. Increased blood iron levels and a p-value of 0.001* were found to indicate a correlation between the MDR-TB and control groups. Additionally, a worse prognosis and more severe tuberculosis TB have been linked to higher CRP values.

According to reports, individuals with more severe lung dysfunction, as shown by lung cavitation, had CRP levels that were noticeably greater than those of patients without cavitation. It has been demonstrated that Mycobacterium tuberculosis and its components induce the release of IL-6 from mononuclear phagocytes in vitro, which is regarded as an inflammatory mediator. There is evidence that IL-6 causes liver acute phase reactants (including CRP).

Numerous clinical and laboratory research have supported the significant correlation between IL-6 and CRP. Bekker and Wood (2010) speculate that the decrease in serum CRP levels that occur during pulmonary tuberculosis treatment may be connected to the resolution of the systemic inflammatory process. This is because the plasma levels of cytokines, such as IL-6, are the principal cytokine that triggers CRP synthesis, which is accompanied by a fall in CRP concentration in patients treated for pulmonary tuberculosis (Bekker & Wood, 2010).

Additionally, it was shown that there was a connection between elevated levels of inflammation and potential bacterial growth and serum iron. Overall, compared to DS, MDR-TB indicates a more severe spectrum of the illness because of higher levels of inflammation and serum iron, both of which are regulated by the haptoglobin 2-2 phenotype. Hp 2-2 and serum iron were positively linked, although Hp 1-1 and Hp 2-1 did not (Table 3). Therefore, regardless of their haptoglobin phenotypes, MTB patients should be advised to avoid drinking alcohol, which has been shown to increase iron stores in the body even at low levels of consumption, and taking iron supplements, both of which have the potential to increase oxidative stress in the body and encourage the growth of co-infecting organisms like MTB and other organisms.

VI. CONCLUSION

All objectives of this study were met. There is little or no work done in this dynamic of using all these parameters and variables such as the haptoglobin phenotype as a severity factor of TB, in relationship to serum iron as well as C-

reactive protein as biomarkers and measures of severity in drug-resistant and sensitive TB in this region of the world. It is important to know all the risk factors, especially on a genetic level, to better understand and manage the disease. The Hp 2-2 gene polymorph is almost exclusive to the African race which would explain the high cases of TB. This Hp 2-2 gene polymorph is associated with raised serum iron levels and is most prevalent in the severity of the MDR-TB patients (but does not predispose to MDR-TB) in TB predictive biomarkers to determine the trend for individuals who contract TB.

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